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ÉSOTÉRISME ET ROMANTISME

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Administration, abonnements :
L'Age d'Homme, S.A.R.L.
5, rue Férou, 75006 Paris – Tél. : 01 55 42 79 79 Fax : 01 40 51 71 02

Association *Politica Hermetica* :
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JOSEPH ENNEMOSER AND MAGNETIC HISTORIOGRAPHY

Wouter J. Hanegraaff

In the context of German Romanticism, mesmerism developed into a direction that was strongly different from what we find in other countries such as France or England. The origins of this specific development can be located very clearly: it all began with a medical theory proposed in 1807 by the respected physician Johann Christian Reil, and adopted by Carl Alexander Ferdinand Kluge in his influential textbook of animal magnetism published in 1811¹. This theory distinguished between two separate but mutually complementary nerve systems, the “cerebral system” (brain and spinal marrow) and the “ganglion system” (centered on the solar plexus), which were presented as the organs of the conscious and the unconscious soul². The basic concept was quickly adopted by a whole series of major authors, including Gotthilf Heinrich von Schubert, Georg Wilhelm Friedrich Hegel, Joseph Ennemoser, Johann Carl Passavant, Dietrich Georg Kieser, Carl Joseph Hieronymus Windischmann, and Justinus Kerner³. They appear to have agreed that through the ganglion system, we have access, in Schubert’s influential formulation, to the mysterious “nightside” of nature⁴. The cerebral system, associated with rational thinking and discursive language, is dominant during our waking life; but its ganglionic counterpart takes over when we fall asleep, and our soul then starts speaking to us in its own “hieroglyphic” and poetic language of images and symbols⁵. However, it was only in the artificial state of somnambulant sleep, or trance, that the ganglion system was seen as revealing its full potential: countless contemporary observers described how patients in such a condition displayed a range of spectacular “occult” or “psychic” abilities, including action-at-distance, hypersensitivity, perception by a “sixth” or inner sense, precognition,

1. Baier, *Meditation und Moderne*, vol. I, p. 190, with reference to Reil, “Über die Eigenschaften”; and Kluge, *Versuch einer Darstellung*, p. 217-219 and 223-267. On the latter, see Gauld, *History of Hypnotism*, p. 99-110. The connection between the ganglion system and magnetism/somnambulism was made by Reil himself (“Über die Eigenschaften,” p. 231-235).
2. The terminology is Reil’s own, although he speaks of “bewusstlos” rather than “unbewusst” (see e.g. “Über die Eigenschaften,” p. 216, 236 and 239).
3. On these authors and their use of the theory, see Baier, *Meditation und Moderne*, vol. I, p. 179-246; Faivre, “Eloquence magique”; Magee, “Hegel on the Paranormal”; Hanegraaff, “A Woman Alone”; Hanegraaff, “Versuch über Friederike Hauffe.”
4. Schubert, *Ansichten*.
5. Schubert, *Symbolik des Traumes*, 1.

clairvoyance, the perception of spirits and angelic beings, speaking and writing in archaic or unknown languages and scripts, and mystical visions of higher worlds and divine realities. The most famous of all these somnambulist patients was Friederike Hauffe, known as “the Seeress of Prevorst,” whose case was described in detail by the poet and physician Justinus Kerner in a bestselling book of 1829¹; but similar phenomena appear to have been observed in countless other patients (almost all of them female), leading to a copious literature and intense discussions among physicians and philosophers².

In the German Romantic literature on somnambulism, the theory of two complementary nerve systems was developed into a full-blown counter-metaphysics directed wholesale against Enlightenment rationalism. In the paradigmatic formulations of Justinus Kerner, the shallow “daylight” world of the rationalist, whose hard “glass skull (tabula vitrea)” keeps him isolated from intuitions of a higher world, stands against the profoundly meaningful “nightside” world of the somnambules, who know from direct experience that behind the brutal realities of social and material existence there is a much larger, all-encompassing, and deeply meaningful life. Hence there are two complementary worlds, or levels of reality, each with its own specific mode of experience and expression: while the Enlightenment reduces everything to cold logic and discursive prose, its alternative expresses itself through profound symbols and poetic language. When our bodily senses shut down temporarily, and we descend into dream or somnambulist trance, our soul “wakes up” to the larger world from whence it has come and where it really belongs³. The rationalist, in contrast, is spiritually asleep. He lives in a state of artificial isolation from his own soul and its powers of perception, incapable of understanding the language of symbols and poetry. He naively believes that his brain and his senses show him all there is, never realizing that they are obstacles rather than reliable instruments for discovering the deeper “secrets of nature.” Blind as he is to her spiritual dimensions, he can only dismiss belief in occult

1. Kerner, *Seherin von Prevorst*. For detailed analysis, see Hanegraaff, “A Woman Alone” and “Versuch”; and Gruber, *Seherin von Prevorst*.
2. For the wider context in Germany, with discussion of several case studies, see Sawicki, *Leben mit den Toten*, p. 131-225. Among the many intellectuals who traveled to Weinsberg to visit Friederike Hauffe were (next to those mentioned in the text) such famous names as Franz von Baader, Joseph Görres, Friedrich Schelling, Friedrich Schleiermacher, and David Friedrich Strauss (for the latter’s account, see Hanegraaff, “A Woman Alone”, p. 246). Important periodicals devoted to somnambulism and related topics were the *Blätter aus Prevorst: Originalien und Lesefrüchte für Freunde des inneren Lebens* (1831-1839) and *Magikon: Archiv für Beobachtungen aus dem Gebiet der Geisterkunde* (1839-1853), both edited by Kerner.
3. This basic Romantic notion has its origin in Reil as well: “Dream is a partial waking; rest in waking is a partial sleep” (“Über die Eigenschaften”, p. 236).

powers and supra-normal abilities as irrational “superstition.” Such abilities are, however, neither miraculous nor supernatural: they are *natural* human faculties, potentially available to us all. Hence, the remarkable feats of somnambules reveal the powers that are latent in humanity, and the first step towards developing them is to reject the limited and limiting reductionist superstitions that have claimed the name of science and reason for themselves.

In appealing to recent medical theories and discoveries, and insisting that these were grounded in empirical facts (*Thatsachen*) ignored by Enlightenment thinkers, German Romantic intellectuals were defending the scientific superiority of an “enchanted” and poetic worldview on paracelsian and theosophical foundations¹. The organic center of the ganglion system was in the hypochondrium (the upper region of the abdomen, marked by the lower ribs), now usually linked to the solar plexus but known in 19th-century Germany as the *Herzgrube*: the heart cavity. For Paracelsus and Johannes Baptista van Helmont, this was the seat of the *archaeus* or “life spirit,” and it assumed a crucial importance in German Romantic mesmerism as well. An earlier mesmerist, Tardy de Montravel, pointed to the *Herzgrube* as the location of the “interior sense” through which direct perception was possible independent of the five exterior senses²; and in fact, this region was constantly highlighted as the main organ of clairvoyant perception in virtuoso somnambulists such as Friederike Hauffe. In other words: against the cold rational knowledge of the brain associated with the cerebral system, the German Romantic mesmerists highlighted the superior spiritual “knowledge of the heart” associated with its ganglionic counterpart. This knowledge included “paranormal” or clairvoyant perception, but went far beyond it to embrace metaphysical realms. Following the micro / macrocosmic correspondence thinking of Paracelsian and Swedenborgian theory, the heart as the center of the human organism corresponded with the sun as the center of the solar system; and this center, in turn, corresponded with the unfathomable light of divinity at the heart of all creation.³ Ultimately, then, the somnambulic

1. On the intellectual origins of Romantic *Naturphilosophie* in what I have called the “alchemical” paradigm, dominated by Paracelsianism and Boehmian theosophy (Hanegraaff, *Esotericism and the Academy*, chapter III), see e. g. Faivre and Zimmermann, *Epochen der Naturmystik*; and Faivre, *Philosophie de la nature*. For the historical backgrounds of mesmerism specifically, see e. g. Benz, *Franz Anton Mesmer*.
2. Baier, *Meditation und Moderne*, vol. I, p. 189-190; Crabtree, *From Mesmer to Freud*, p. 58.
3. For excellent examples, see Friederike Hauffe’s so-called “Solar Circle” and “Circle of Life”: circular diagrams that represented her outer and inner life, and revolved around the “Gnaden Sonne” (sun of grace) in the center. See discussion in Hanegraaff, “Versuch” (part I), p. 1-36; “Human Potential before Esalen”, p. 30-38 (with reproductions of the circles). The correspondence of “heart” and “sun” as the centers of the individual organism, the physical solar system, and metaphysical reality, were undoubtedly influenced by the teachings of Emanuel Swedenborg (see Hanegraaff, *Swedenborg, Oetinger, Kant*, p. 51-55).

knowledge of the heart was understood as a *gnosis* about divine things, infinitely superior to the merely rational knowledge of the brain and the testimonies of the exterior senses¹.

By presenting “daylight” rationality as a limited instrument powerless to grasp the deeper “nightside” truths accessible to the soul, or explain the empirical facts of consciousness revealed in somnambulant trance – the Romantic mesmerists had discovered a line of argumentation that stood all the principles of Enlightenment philosophy and science on their head. One century later, its essence would be formulated in all simplicity by their most influential modern successor, Carl Gustav Jung: “my soul cannot be the object of my judgment and knowledge – rather, my judgment and knowledge are objects of my soul.”² Anybody who accepted such an epistemological hierarchy was forced to rethink a whole series of dualisms constitutive of Enlightenment rationalism, as will be seen. Most important for our present concerns, however, are the *historiographical* implications: anything that Enlightenment historiography had sought to consign to the wastebasket of history – magic, divination, clairvoyance, symbolism, the occult – now came to be perceived as manifestations of the soul and its hidden powers, and highlighted as *central* to the historical development of human culture! At the same time, however, because anything pertaining to the soul was believed to be of universal and eternal validity, historicity and temporality themselves were downplayed in favor of timeless truths, and mere “external events” in favor of their “inner essence.” One can see this clearly, for example, in one of the earliest German Romantic authors who attempted to sketch a history of “magnetism,” Johann Carl Passavant. Along Hegelian lines, he introduced that history as follows:

Of the history of humanity we know almost nothing but the outer occurrence, the dead letter, the skeleton of times. The life-giving spirit that moved individuals and entire generations, and is expressed only as half-understandable ciphers in deeds and world-events, remains inaccessible to historical research. This is why the more we investigate the wellsprings of human spiritual activity, out of dissatisfaction with mere external phenomena, and descend into the deeper recesses of our inner self, where spiritual treasures lie hidden, the oftener do we find the books of the past to be closed to us, the more hieroglyphic does their writing appear to us. For example, we hear of men who, through their profound insights into the essence of things, through their inspired speech, or through laudable deeds, were like bright stars to their contemporaries; but what is most important – the spiritual roots of these phenomena, the light that illuminated those elect ones,

1. See Hanegraaff, “Magnetic Gnosis.”

2. Jung, *The Red Book*, Liber Primus, vol. II, cap. I.

the power that inspired them, the motivation for their great deeds – we can hardly guess. The mortal eye perceives only the dial of time, not the clockwork that moves the hour hands¹.

In the second part of his monograph on magnetism and somnambulism, Passavant sketched its historical antecedents among the Israelites, Indians, Greeks and Romans, Nordic peoples, and in Christianity. In what sounds like a far echo of Augustine in his *Retractationes*², he emphasized that Christianity “should not be seen as a new doctrine,” and hence cannot be compared with any other historical religion, but was the fullest and purest manifestation of “the absolute and eternal religion.”

The most influential and representative “magnetic historiographer” from the German Romantic period was, however, the Tirolean physician Joseph Ennemoser (1787-1854)³. Raised in a pious Roman Catholic environment, as a young man he traveled through Italy and Austria but returned to Innsbruck to study physics and medicine. In 1809 he took part in the Tirolean war of liberation against France and Bayern, and after some further peregrinations ended up in Berlin, where he continued his medical studies under Fichte, Reil (the inventor of the ganglionic theory), and other major authorities on mesmerism including Christoph Wilhelm Hufeland and Karl Christian Wolfart. After further military adventures – he was rewarded for his courage with an iron cross –, in 1814 he returned to Berlin to finish his studies in medicine. In the following years he worked on his large history of magnetism, published in 1819⁴, and in the same year was appointed professor in the medical faculty of the University of Bonn – the center of German Romantic *Naturphilosophie*. From 1837 on he worked as a physician, first in Innsbruck and from 1841 to his death in Munich, during which time he cultivated his contacts with thinkers like Kerner and Schubert. A completely reworked version of his history of magnetism appeared in 1844 under the new title *Geschichte der Magie*, and it is on this work that I will further concentrate⁵.

In a recent monograph, I have argued that the earliest attempts at a historical conceptualization of “Western esotericism” emerged from the so-called “anti-

1. Passavant, *Untersuchungen über den Lebensmagnetismus*, 272-272. Generally on Passavant and his importance, see Baier, *Meditation und Moderne*, vol. I, p. 210-218.

2. Augustine, *Retractationes* I, XII, 3.

3. For Ennemoser’s biography, see Boegner, “Joseph Ennemosers Leben und Werk;” and de Rachewiltz, *Joseph Ennemoser*. His anthropology has been analyzed in detail by Schweizer, *Anthropologie der Romantik*, p. 610-693.

4. Ennemoser, *Der Magnetismus*.

5. Ennemoser, *Geschichte der Magie*. A systematic comparison with the first version of 1819 would be extremely interesting, but because the final 1844 edition (and its English translation of 1854) has been much more influential, I must here concentrate on the latter.

apologetic” historiography that was pioneered by the historian of philosophy Jacob Thomasius in his *Schediasma historicum* of 1665¹. In short, Thomasius attacked the “apologetic” tradition of Roman Catholic Theology since Justin Martyr, Clement of Alexandria, Origen, and Eusebius of Caesarea, which had sought to integrate “pagan” philosophical traditions in Christian theology in the context of a *prisca theologia* or *philosophia perennis*. Against this approach, anti-apologeticism made a strict distinction between the true religion of biblical Christianity, the limited but legitimate study of philosophy based upon natural reason, and the heretical tradition of pagan philosophy. The latter was based upon the heretical doctrine of the eternity of the world, and on the equally heretical idea that human beings had a natural ability to gain access to the very mysteries of the divine being, through “gnosis.” Anti-apologeticism was at the basis of Ehregott Daniel Colberg’s Protestant heresiological construct of “Platonic-Hermetic Christianity” and Jacob Brucker’s history of “*philosophia sectaria*” in his enormously influential *Historia critica philosophiae* of 1742-1744². From these perspectives, the domain that we nowadays refer to as “Western esotericism” was interpreted as the continuation of pagan religion concealed as Christianity.

Against these Protestant and Enlightenment approaches, the Roman Catholic and Romantic physician Ennemoser now presented a history based on entirely different foundations: his ambition was to show that magnetic phenomena and somnambulist states had been central to the development of human consciousness since the beginning of history. The question of Platonic or pagan influences on Christianity played no structural role in his story; but science and natural philosophy had become the basic framework. In sharp contrast with Enlightenment naturalism or positivism, however, Ennemoser’s Romantic/mesmerist *Naturphilosophie* was based upon a concept of “living nature” (Faivre) permeated by invisible, occult, “mysterious and incalculable powers” (Weber). He emphasized that these powers were neither supernatural nor demonic in origin, as claimed by traditional Christianity, but no superstitious illusions either, as claimed by Enlightenment rationalism: rather, they should be seen as manifestations of the “inner” and more profound night side of nature, that reveals itself only when “daylight consciousness,” dominated by the rational brain and the exterior senses, is temporarily suppressed. It is important to realize how easily such a thesis harmonized with the pietist sensibilities that had been cultivated in German culture since the 17th century. Somnambulist

1. Hanegraaff, *Esotericism and the Academy*, chapter II; and see the crucial study by Lehmann-Brauns, *Weisheit in der Weltgeschichte*.
2. Hanegraaff, “Philosophy’s Shadow”.

states were extremely similar to the “divine ecstasies” (*göttliche Entzückungen*) that had been highlighted by Philipp Jakob Spener with reference to the apostle Paul, and criticized as *Schwärmerei* or “enthusiasm” by critics; and already Colberg had emphasized the tendency of the “enthusiasts” to distinguish each and every thing into “external” and “internal” (the inner church, inner word, inner heaven, and so on). Add to this the evident dependence of Romantic mesmerism and *Naturphilosophie* on the German traditions of Paracelsianism and Christian theosophy, and it is clear that in Ennemoser’s history of magic, we have the “Hermetic-Platonic” answer to Colberg and Brucker.

Ennemoser’s understanding of *Magie* or *Magismus* comes straight out of the Renaissance tradition of *magia naturalis* understood as a *prisca magia*, including its emphasis on the classic concept of ἰδιότητες ἄρρητοι (which had included magnetism already in antiquity¹) or occult qualities in the wider context of *philosophia occulta*. He never gives a sharp definition of magic, but clearly presents it as the “ancient wisdom” as such, referring to it as the “sum of all secret wisdom,” and adopting the conventional distinction between true divine magic and evil or superstitious *goeteia* (*Zauberei*, or sorcery)². The most significant innovation lies in his emphasis – which announces the progressive psychologization of mesmerism through the 19th century – that the true magic “lies in the most secret and innermost powers of the mind³”. Suggesting a notion of progress “from magic to science” while adapting it to his own ends, Ennemoser states that the genuinely scientific study of these powers began only with Mesmer, and hence his history of magic proper is restricted to the previous, pre-scientific stage⁴. His emphasis on the mind is evident in his general introduction “on magic and its parts in general”, which is dominated by three long chapters about visions, dreams, and prophecy/divination (*das Wahrsagen*) as the central manifestations of “magic:” although Ennemoser believes strongly in action at distance and the power of mind over matter, and distinguishes between “visionary” (*schauende*) and “active” (*wirkende*) magic⁵, he is ultimately most interested in magic as a means of achieving “higher (or deeper) knowledge” of the world.

Clearly representative of German historiographical approaches in the wake of Herder, Ennemoser thinks of history in terms of the achievements of

1. Röhr, *Der okkulte Kraftbegriff im Altertum*.

2. Ennemoser, *Geschichte der Magie*, p. 65-66 (including the terminology of “white” versus “black” magic).

3. *Ibid.*, p. xxvii. See also e. g. p. xix, xxvii, 273-275, 278-281 and 752.

4. Ennemoser’s *Geschichte der Magie* was presented as the first part of a larger *Geschichte des thierischen Magnetismus*, but the second part devoted to the “scientific” stage was never published.

5. E. g. *Ibid.*, p. 67, 69 and 277.

successive “peoples.” He divides it into three parts: the “ancient world” (the Oriental peoples, the Egyptians, the Israelites), the world of the Greeks and Romans, and the “Germanic world” (from the ancient Germans and nordic peoples through the middle ages and the Renaissance, continuing into the present). If one steps back to consider the course of “history as a whole,” in a visionary *Gesamtschau*¹, its events appear to be far from random and can be described in terms of lawful organic development. History then reveals itself as a deeply meaningful drama in several acts: it narrates the story of how, with many twists and turns, the inborn potential of human consciousness slowly but certainly comes to full realization, according to God’s providential design². Similar to Lessing’s famous *Erziehung des Menschengeschlechts*, Ennemoser’s leading metaphor is that of an individual’s life: humanity progresses from birth and childhood through adolescence to full maturity. But he also keeps using the metaphor of a tree that develops from its seeds and roots into a trunk that finally carries branches and flowers, and that of a stage drama: at given moments in time, a new people “steps on to the stage of history” to play the part that Providence has written for it. Ennemoser never thinks of “external” events as causal factors in history: on the contrary, the true cause of any outward “manifestation” always lies in an inward necessity, “essence,” or germinal “idea”³, and in true Hegelian fashion, individuals and their actions are ultimately just the instruments through which the World Spirit is realizing itself:

with steady pace, like a succession of a kingdom’s dynasties, history marches forward in a chain of peoples (*Völkern*), each one of which, in increasing power and at ever greater length, builds upon the ruins of its predecessor to claim world domination and represent the peak of the World Spirit for the length of its existence, until it is ousted by the next⁴.

The most ancient peoples were literally in an infantile state. Humanity still “hung on to nature by the umbilical chord and sat in the Creator’s lap⁵.” It lived in a barely conscious, dreamlike state of innocence, intimately one with nature. “Magical” states of mind were more common than today, and because man’s inner sense, “yet undisturbed by reflection, was still more open to the voice of nature,” he lived his life in the peaceful harmony of “the endless depth of an untroubled mind⁶”. The presence of divinity was still experienced

1. E. g. *Ibid.*, p. 29 and 264-267.

2. E. g. *Ibid.*, p. 264-266, 441-442 and 467-468.

3. E. g. *Ibid.*, p. 45-46, 260-263, 357, 479 and 705.

4. *Ibid.*, p. 706 (quoting Carl Friedrich Haug, *Allgemeine Geschichte* [1841], without page nr.).

5. *Ibid.*, p. 300.

6. *Ibid.*, p. 32-33.

everywhere in nature, humanity stood under the benevolent guidance of an ideal priesthood, and “God, the Seers, and the Poets” spoke through a superior ur-language of symbolic images¹. Ennemoser has to admit that there was also “superstition and idolatry,” but hardly dwells on it: “Faith, love and obedience were everywhere the pillars²”.

Because Ennemoser sees magic as a universal phenomenon rooted in natural human abilities, he does not trace it back to Persia but emphasizes its presence throughout the ancient Orient, including India and China³. His long discussions of magic among the oriental peoples focus on ecstatic visionary states and healing arts practiced in temples by a spiritually enlightened priesthood. Ennemoser argues that the ancient forms of temple healing were based upon a “natural science” whose basic principles were the same as those of modern mesmerism⁴. The “secret doctrines” (*Geheimlehren*) concerning such practices were preserved by priestly elites and transmitted through mystery initiations and mythical narratives. Egypt represents the highest development of magic during this first, oriental period, and it is from here that many later Greek philosophers derived much of their wisdom⁵. Ultimately, however, the great oriental cultures had no future, because they lacked any sense of history and development: Ennemoser compares them with a mummy, whose body has neither decayed nor grown and developed through the centuries⁶. There was, however, one exception. The people of Israel was destined to become the oriental “root” or “stem” from which humanity would grow through adolescence to maturity:

In the ancient, true sense of the word, Judaism is the real tree of life of the inner, genetically progressing development of culture. All the other pagan peoples with their various religious systems are twigs torn off from the great tree of life: although they vegetate, they are capable of no inner development (*Wachsthum*). Judaism is the real Mysterium, which in Christianity attained the ideal state of sanctity and reunion with God [*Gottesvereinigung*]⁷.

1. *Ibid.*, p. 41-52.

2. *Ibid.*, p. 46 (cf. p. 65 about the necessary qualities of the ancient sages: “Justice, truth and a spirit of service”).

3. *Ibid.*, 64-68 (including criticism of Brucker), p. 300 and 303.

4. *Ibid.*, p. 281-399.

5. *Ibid.*, p. 222-226 and 364-366.

6. *Ibid.*, p. 282, cf. p. 264.

7. *Ibid.*, p. 62. For the idea of pagan religions “breaking off” from the main trunk, see also p. 120-122 about the Sons of Noah, where Ennemoser quotes Jacob Böhme as the key to understanding the “true development of history”. The descendants of Cham are the worst of the worst: “Nowhere does one find such spiritual numbness, such a coarse soul and such alienation from God [*Gottesverlassenheit*] as among the black race of Africa and, as seems

The Jews, with their forward-looking mentality, developed a new kind of magic based upon a humble reliance on divine grace rather than the *hubris* of human autonomy¹. Since Ennemoser always emphasizes “inner” processes rather than external causality, it is easy for him to avoid a dependence of Judaism on pagan Egypt: although they spent so much time in that country, the Jews adopted very little of its magical traditions². The role of kabbalah in Ennemoser’s narrative remains somewhat unclear: he discusses it not in his chapter on “the Old Covenant” (which concentrates on dreams, visions, and trances in the Old Testament), but in the introductory parts of his book,³ and his understanding of the topic appears to be based entirely on Franz Joseph Molitor’s famous *Philosophie der Geschichte oder über die Tradition* (1827-1839), which is quoted extensively⁴. In line with this source, Ennemoser hardly bothers to differentiate between Jewish and Christian manifestations: to explain what kabbalah is all about, he freely refers to such authorities as Reuchlin, Knorr von Rosenroth, Paracelsus, Böhme, Pordage, Pasqually, Saint-Martin, Henry More, Schelling, and Baader.

The central event in Ennemoser’s history of consciousness is the appearance of Jesus Christ, through whom Judaism fulfils its historical destiny: that of giving birth to the “absolute religion,” which is limited no longer to just one people but brings together humanity as a whole⁵. Through another instrument of Providence, Alexander the Great, the political foundations for this unity had already been created, and the capital of Alexandria became the nodal point for the further development of magic. Ennemoser’s discussions of Greek culture demonstrate how strongly he associates the Greeks with myth, rather than with rational philosophy: for him, Greek culture is essentially “poetic,” which means that it is thoroughly “magical”⁶. With constant reference to the physicist and chemist Johann Salomo Christoph Schweigger and his influential *Einleitung in die Mythologie* (1836), he argues that myth uses the “poetry of nature” to speak about natural forces⁷: symbols are “archetypal [*urbildliche*] representations

certain, among the wild tribes of South-America and Australia that were transported from there” (p. 123).

1. *Ibid.*, p. 429-432.

2. *Ibid.*, p. 426.

3. *Ibid.*, p. 71-96.

4. *Ibid.*, p. 72-85. On Molitor’s many connections with contemporary Christian theosophy and *Naturphilosophie*, see Koch, *Franz Joseph Molitor*.

5. Ennemoser, *Geschichte der Magie*, p. 461.

6. *Ibid.*, p. 484: “Das ganze Griechenthum ist eine lebendige Magie, [...] denn das Griechenthum ist durchaus poetischer Natur.”

7. *Ibid.*, p. 616-703. On Schweigger’s work, see von Engelhardt, “Naturforschung als Mythologie und Mission”.

of how the spirit reveals itself, and truer than the knowledge of systematic reflection”¹. The true source of poetry is nature herself:

For Nature is essentially poetic, higher and deeper than anything of which human fantasy is capable; in her wondrous manifestations she is the expression, by means of images, of the divine creations; a voice of God, to which man should give attention, in order to be aware of the wonders that occur all the time in the world around him. Only the faithful observer and worshiper of Nature, who traces her signs and listens to her voices, gets to know the hidden laws of Nature... while the rest of the world, as if half asleep, gets ever more alienated from the divine and sinks away in illusion and superstition. That is why all the great natural scientists have always been truly pious people; that is why the magnetic clairvoyant, waking up in sleep from the daylight dream, through his deeper insight into the secret workings of Nature and her symbols breaks out in ecstatic admiration, in poetic utterings and songs of praise – just as in the poetic time of beginnings, when knowledge about Nature, poetry, and religion were still one².

Flourishing in Alexandria, Neoplatonic “eclecticism” was the essential medium through which all the magical traditions of the declining pagan world were transmitted to Christianity³. In evaluating this phenomenon positively, as a crucial step in the continuation of ancient magical wisdom, Ennemoser integrates the *philosophia perennis* into a novel framework of providentialist evolutionism.

Ennemoser states that Christianity’s task was to “disenchant the world” while “restoring the true magic⁴”, and this may sound puzzling unless one is familiar with the specifics of German terminology. *Entzauberung* uses the term *Zauberei*, conventionally translated as “sorcery” and associated with the negative counterpart of natural magic: the idolatrous and superstitious practices known as *goeteia*. In the final part of his book, Ennemoser traces the history of true magic (*Magie*) – that is to say, the natural magic based on magnetism – in what he sees as the “Germanic” period, but much of his attention goes to its negative counterpart: the various forms of demonic or idolatrous superstition of the middle ages, culminating in the witchcraft craze. In these discussions, his essentially scientific agenda becomes more and more evident. It is clear to Ennemoser that belief in witchcraft was a tragic mass delusion, and he does not want to spend much time on phenomena that may be associated with “magic” but cannot easily be interpreted in terms of magnetism, such as “spirit-conjurors

1. Ennemoser, *Geschichte der Magie*, p. 621.

2. *Ibid.*, p. 635-636.

3. *Ibid.*, p. 599-601, and cf. p. 714-715.

4. *Ibid.*, p. 709.

and exorcists, treasure-diggers and alchemical goldmakers, astrological and hermetic mystagogues like the Rosicrucians etc., horoscope-makers, Illuminati and cartomancers, necromancers and mirror-prophets etc.¹”. He does devote some discussion to Christian theosophers known for their ecstatic or trance-like states, like John Pordage, Thomas Bromley, Antoinette Bourguignon, Jane Leade, Pierre Poiret, and Emanuel Swedenborg, but his ambiguity is obvious: he admits that most of what they do pertains to magic in the good sense, but feels he has to warn against the risk of getting lost “in the fanatical darkness of spiritual adepts²”. Not surprisingly, the true lineage of post-medieval magic up to Mesmer begins with the physicians Paracelsus and the elder Van Helmont, continuing from there to authors like Agrippa, Fludd, Campanella, Kircher (important because of his work on the magnet) plus a range of Paracelsians, and ending with Gassner, Cagliostro and Swedenborg in the 18th century. However, Ennemoser ends his book with “the arch-magus in the true sense”, who has gained a deeper insight into “the life and spirit of humanity” than anyone else: the “true German and Christian theosopher” Jacob Böhme³. Now that Böhme’s work has been rediscovered⁴ and Mesmer has put “magic” on a scientific foundation, Enlightenment rationalism will soon prove to be a transitory phenomenon, and we can look towards the future with the greatest confidence:

The ancient Orient [...] appears to us, so to speak, as a living image of the primitive childhood of the past. The Greek-Roman world was a fleeting phenomenon, like the contemporary moment, but an endless future still lies ahead for the German spirit. The history of the world so far has merely provided it with the elements for an endless spiritual activity. Therefore, if the Orient has often been compared with childhood, the time of the Greeks and Romans with the living movement and vitality of the adolescent, and the Germanic one with mature manhood, this comparison is true insofar as with German history, maturity is only just beginning: Germanhood has a whole new future ahead of it, first to complete its own formation, and then to become a leader and teacher of the peoples and the times. [...] [T]he Greeks and Romans were just the momentary means of transmission between old and new; and the Orient, already sunk into stagnation and into the night of the past, is dreaming in a thousand-year sleep of death, until one day, stirred up by the new Germanic spirit of the future, it will wake up to fresh new life again⁵.

1. *Ibid.*, p. 836.

2. *Ibid.*, p. 879.

3. *Ibid.*, p. 966.

4. On the rediscovery of Böhme in German Romanticism, see e. g. Viatte, *Sources occultes*; Benz, *Sources mystiques*; Mayer, *Jena Romanticism*; Magee, *Hegel and the Hermetic Tradition*.

5. Ennemoser, *Geschichte der Magie*, p. 264-265.

This must suffice as an overview of Ennemoser's German Romantic vision. In conclusion, I would like to emphasize three innovative features: (1) his use of *mesmerism/somnambulism* as the heuristic "key" for tracing the history of magic, (2) his *evolutionist/providentialist* vision, and (3) the *religionist* nature of his approach in general.

The first point stands in stark contrast with previous historiographies of "Western esotericism," which had concentrated essentially on philosophical or religious ideas and opinions, and had been concerned with the history of the true religious doctrine or the conflict between pagan or heretical concepts and biblical theology. None of that was of any importance to Ennemoser: his concern was, quite simply, to show that the phenomena of magnetism and somnambulant trance were nothing new but had existed since the earliest childhood of humanity. In making that claim, he became the chief pioneer of a new genre of "occult historiography." Within ten years, his book was published in an English translation¹. and by that time, the Scottish lawyer John Campbell Colquhoun – who had studied in Germany and was very familiar with the tradition of *Naturphilosophie* – had already published his own *History of Magic, Witchcraft, and Animal Magnetism* in two volumes (1851)². Along very similar lines as Ennemoser, he traced the history of magnetism a.k.a. magic from the Chaldaean magi to Mesmer, but without the heavy evolutionist/providentialist slant. In the "waste land" of the later 19th century, his book was one among the very few that made it possible for readers to place the various manifestations of "the occult" within a reasonably clear historical narrative from antiquity to the present.

1. Ennemoser's history was translated in 1854 by William Howitt, as *History of Magic*, with an appendix devoted to stories of "apparitions, dreams, second sight, somnambulism, predictions, divination, witchcraft, vampires, fairies, table-turning, and spirit-rapping" compiled by his wife Mary (on this remarkable couple and their work, see Oppenheim, *The Other World*, p. 36-38). Ennemoser became one of the most frequently plagiarized sources of Helena P. Blavatsky's *Isis Unveiled*: with no less than 107 passages, Emmette Coleman ("Sources of Madame Blavatsky's Writings", p. 356) ranked him second place, after the 134 passages from Dunlap's *Sod: The Son of Man*. For the influence of Ennemoser on Blavatsky, see also Baier, *Meditation und Moderne*, vol. I, p. 258-261; and for the more general influence of German mesmerism on occultism, see *ibid.*, p. 277-282. The relation between German Romantic mesmerism and Blavatsky, by mediation of English authors who had studied the sources in the original language, deserves further study: in *The Theosophical Enlightenment*, Joscelyn Godwin has highlighted Blavatsky's debt to Enlightenment mythography, but to understand her evolutionism and her pervasive references to the mesmeric fluid, sources such as Wilkins' Ennemoser translation or the works of John Campbell Colquhoun (see text) may be equally important. In 1836, the latter had even published a study of animal magnetism under the title *Isis Revelata!*
2. On Colquhoun, see also Baier, *Meditation und Moderne*, vol. I, p. 212, 245, 258 and 282.

In the last decade of the century, we find essentially the same approach in a series of large and erudite works on the history of “occultism” and the “occult sciences” published by an elusive private scholar, Carl Kieseewetter (1854-1895)¹. Similar to A. E. Waite in the anglophone world, Kieseewetter’s impressive erudition made him into the virtually unavoidable German authority for history of “the occult”. In the Introduction to his first large volume, *Geschichte des neueren Occultismus* (1891), he defined “occultism” as concerned with “all those phenomena of nature and the soul (*des Natur- und Seelenlebens*) that have not yet been generally recognized by official science [and] whose causes are hidden from the senses²”. In other words: writing the history of “occultism” meant tracing how earlier generations had practiced and theorized about the “psychic” or “paranormal” phenomena that were currently the object of parapsychology or psychical research. Thus, for example, Kieseewetter’s first chapter focused on Agrippa’s ideas about such topics as telepathy, dreams, clairvoyance, hypnosis, ecstasy, the magical power of the will, and the mesmeric or magnetic life force; and he went on to trace these themes through essentially the same series of 16th-18th century authors that had been discussed by Ennemoser. But he also discussed Ennemoser himself, and continued with 19th-century spiritualism and psychical research up to and including Carl du Prel. After three smaller books on the Faust figure, John Dee, and Mesmer himself (all published in 1893), Kieseewetter began to push his investigations ever farther back into the past, resulting in a large volume on the history of alchemy, astrology, and magic (*Die Geheimwissenschaften*, 1895) and another one on the occult in antiquity (*Der Occultismus des Altertums*, vol. I, 1896). Kieseewetter’s books became standard references in the field, at least in the German-speaking world, and deserve more study in their own right, but for our present concerns we can dispense with a detailed analysis. It suffices that, similar to A. E. Waite’s volumes, they are essentially works of erudition that give the reader access to otherwise obscure materials, often by means of lengthy quotations; and that, like Ennemoser’s

1. Almost nothing is known about Kieseewetter’s life and career. He lived with his mother in a small town, Meiningen, and was a regular contributor to the important occultist journal *Die Sphinx*. Max Dessoir remembered him as a large bald man with a red face, who was “anything but an ascetic or navel-gazer” but, rather, “was living quite a wild life” and had no patience for pious upper-class ladies swooning over the occult: “Remarkable about Kieseewetter is that he was faithful like a child when it came to ancient manuscripts, but a stubborn and mocking sceptic about reports from his own time” (*Buch der Erinnerung*, p. 129-130). Emil Bock claims that Kieseewetter “ate and drank himself to death” (*Rudolf Steiner*, p. 173-174), but according to a persistent rumor that I have been unable to confirm or disconfirm, his premature death at age 41 was caused by a failed experiment with the witches’ salve.
2. Kieseewetter, *Geschichte des neueren Okkultismus*, p. 13. The formulation echoes the third objective of the Theosophical Society, of which Kieseewetter was a member: “To investigate unexplained laws of Nature and the powers latent in man.”

and Colquhoun's, their intention is to provide contemporary research into the "paranormal" with a solid historical pedigree. From such a perspective, "Western esotericism" was no longer understood in terms of a syncretism between pagan / platonic ideas and biblical Christianity, but as comprising the sum of historical evidence for the mysterious powers of nature and the human mind prematurely discarded by the Enlightenment.

Moving on to the second innovative feature of Ennemoser's *Geschichte der Magie*: as far as the history of "Western esotericism" is concerned, it was the exemplary and pioneering example of a new type of historiography typical of the Romantic period. It was neither a narrative of decline or continuity of the "ancient wisdom" (as in the *prisca theologia* and *philosophia perennis* tradition); nor was it an exercise in intellectual history, based on the assumption that to understand the ideas of specific authors or currents, one must put them in their historical context and investigate the influences upon them (as in the histories of Colberg and Brucker). Contrary to the former approach, Ennemoser presented his readers with a teleological narrative of spiritual progress by means of evolution, which endowed the very fact of historical change and development with profound spiritual meaning and import; and contrary to the latter, he rejected "external" causation in favor of the "inner" drives and dynamics of divine providence, or God's plan with humanity. As far as academic research is concerned, historiographies of this type would only very gradually lose their credibility along with the general decline of Romanticism and German Idealism during and after the 19th century. They were, however, adopted with great enthusiasm by occultist authors, and have remained popular in esoteric and New Age circles to the present day¹.

For the third innovative feature of Ennemoser's work, it is useful to compare him with Gottfried Arnold's famous history of churches and heretics. The latter was grounded in a radical pietist rejection of sterile dogmatic dispute in favour of direct spiritual experience². Following exactly the same logic, Ennemoser attacked the "cerebral thinking" of the self-appointed "schoolmasters" and

1. On the importance of Romantic evolutionism to nineteenth-century esotericism, see Hanegraaff, *New Age Religion*, p. 462-482, and *cf.* p. 302-330 for the point that even New Age visions of historical evolution still tend to focus on a "Platonic-Orientalist" lineage through Egypt and the Essenes to Christianity: "the Christian west is consistently highlighted as the center stage for those historical events which have been essential to humanity's spiritual evolution" (*ibid.*, p. 303). For Ennemoser's influence on H.P. Blavatsky's evolutionist theosophy, see above, note 55. A particularly clear example of latter-day Romantic (neo-Hegelian) evolutionism is Ken Wilber's transpersonal historiography in *Up From Eden* (1983).
2. On Arnold's foundational importance for "religionism", see Hanegraaff, *Esotericism and the Academy*, chapter II.

“policemen” of reason¹, with their endless quarreling over mere words and abstractions. Both authors agreed that what mattered in history was not the dead letter but the living spirit, not outward doctrines but inward experience, not the knowledge of the brain but the knowledge of the heart. This similarity is not accidental, but reflects a structural commonality grounded in German Pietist sensibilities. Arnold’s historiography was based upon the concept of a radical incommensurability between “Athens” (reason) and “Jerusalem” (faith), which simply do not speak the same language and share no common ground; and the same logic of incommensurability governs Ennemoser’s contrast between the discursive “daytime” consciousness of the brain and the experiential “nightside” consciousness of the soul. Arnold argued that faith had nothing in common with reason; and similarly, Ennemoser saw no point in using the language of the brain to speak about the truths of the soul. Both authors would have readily agreed that when it comes to spiritual realities, critical debate is useless: there is simply no alternative for direct spiritual experience.

As a result, neither Arnold nor Ennemoser was able (or willing) to look at historical developments from the perspective of social context, external influences on the genesis or development of ideas, or contingent factors: all those were clearly irrelevant or, at best, of secondary importance. But nevertheless, both claimed to be writing history. This peculiar combination is typical of an approach known as “religionism,” and it should now be clear that Ennemoser’s work represents an important new development in the history of that phenomenon after Arnold. The principal difference between the two is Ennemoser’s evolutionism, which was really something new. Arnold’s perspective had allowed for no real development of “Christianity” at all, because absolute truth has no history; Ennemoser, however, could claim that whereas the truths of nature and the soul were indeed eternal, man’s capacity to *understand* them had developed dramatically over the course of the centuries. A very similar vision would be defended in the 20th-century from the perspective of psychology, particularly in the work of Carl Gustav Jung²; but that would be the topic for another article.

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1. For invectives against such thinking, see e. g. Ennemoser, *Geschichte der Magie*, p. VII-X, 36, 63, 265 and 271.
 2. Hanegraaff, *Esotericism and the Academy*, chapter IV.

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